

1 Main components and human health risks assessment of
2 PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁ in two areas influenced by cement
3 plants

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50 **Abstract**

51

52 Particulate matter (PM) is widely recorded as a source of diseases, being more harmful
53 those particles with smaller size. PM is released to the environment as a consequence of
54 different activities, being one of them cement production. The objective of this pilot
55 study was to characterize PM of different sizes around cement facilities to have a
56 preliminary approach of their origin, and evaluate their potential health risks. For that
57 purpose, three fractions of PM (10, 2.5, and 1) were collected in the nearby area of two
58 cement plants with different backgrounds (urban and rural) in different seasons.
59 Subsequently, main components, outdoor and indoor concentrations, exposure, and
60 human health risks were assessed. Greatest levels of PM₁, organic matter, and metals
61 were found in urban location, especially in winter. Consequently, environmental
62 exposure and human health risks registered their highest values in the urban plant
63 during wintertime. Exposure was higher for indoor activities, expressing some metals
64 their peak values in the PM₁ fraction. Non-carcinogenic risks were below the safety
65 threshold (HQ<1). Carcinogenic risks for most of the metals were below the limit of 10⁻⁵,
66 except for Cr (VI), which exceeded it in both locations, but being in the range
67 considered as assumable (10⁻⁶-10⁻⁴).

68

69 *Key words*

70

71 Cement

72 Particulate matter fractions

73 Indoor and outdoor exposure

74 Human health risk

75

76 *Highlights*

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- 78 ➤ Characterisation of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁ was carried out around two cement
- 79 plants.
- 80 ➤ Outdoor and indoor exposure and human health risk to toxic elements were
- 81 assessed.
- 82 ➤ Higher concentrations and human health risks were observed in urban site in
- 83 winter.
- 84 ➤ Maximum human health risk levels were found due to PM₁ fraction exposure.

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1. Introduction

World Health Organization has recently estimated that ambient pollution is responsible for 3.7 million premature deaths yearly (WHO, 2014). Among the substances comprising air pollution, particulate matter (PM) is seen by some studies as the most harmful (Cohen et al., 2005; EEA, 2013). PM can cause a wide variety of health impacts, such as asthma, bronchitis, cardiovascular diseases, and lung cancer (Čupr et al., 2013).

Most influent parameters in PM hazardous potential are size and chemical composition (Harrison and Yin, 2000). PM size range spreads from micrometers to nanometres. PM with a diameter smaller than 10 μm (PM_{10}) are able to enter into the respiratory tract and reach the lungs (US EPA, 2013). The coarse fraction of these particles, those with a diameter between 10 and 2.5 μm ($\text{PM}_{10-2.5}$), remains in the upper part of the respiratory tract, while the fine particles, those PM smaller than 2.5 μm ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$), can undergo deeper in the lung system, being the smallest fraction capable of reaching the bloodstream (Anderson et al., 2012). The potential effects that can be developed after entering into the circulatory system could be more pernicious, concluding several publications (Cifuentes et al., 2000; Schwartz et al., 1996) that the smaller the PM, the more harmful it is. Regarding their chemical composition, the presence of toxic substances (e.g. acids, metals, and PAHs), plays an important role in health impacts (Casseo et al., 2013). PM size and chemical composition depend on several parameters, such as the weather, period of the year, and emission source (Casseo et al., 2013).

One of the industrial activities that releases PM into the environment is the cement production (Gupta et al., 2012; Predicatori et al., 2009). In this activity, PM are generated as a consequence of subjecting lime to high temperatures (from 900 to 1,500°C) for yielding cement (EU Commission, 2013). Furthermore, raw materials processing and clinker milling and packaging could lead to PM fugitive emissions (Abdul-Wahab, 2006). Currently, there are few papers focusing on the study of health risks produced by PM around cement facilities (Abdul-Wahab, 2006; Rovira et al., 2015, 2014, 2011a). Although it is stated that almost 50% of the PM emitted from the cement industry is smaller than 2.5 μm (Gupta et al., 2012), no one of the previous cited articles is focused on the fine fraction of particles.

The aim of this study is to characterize PM around cement facilities to have a preliminary approach of their origin and assess their potential risk for human health. For that purpose, three PM fractions (10, 2.5, and 1) were collected in the surrounding of two cement factories. Concentrations of metals, ions, and carbon were measured in order to better know the main PM components. Human health risks were evaluated having into account the carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risks derived from the particles metal content. To our knowledge, this is the first study focused in revealing potential health effects of PM fine fraction in the surrounding of cement facilities.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Site description and PM monitoring

The two studied facilities are located in Catalonia (Northeast Spain). The first one (A) is placed in Barcelona metropolitan area, within an urban sector profoundly affected by a

150 number of different industries. Moreover, the settlement is crossed by two highways
151 with an average daily traffic of 49,199 and 160,558 vehicles per day, respectively
152 (Ministerio de Fomento, 2012). The plant has been operating there since 1917, and as a
153 consequence of the substantial development of the town in recent decades, the distance
154 from the facility to some neighbourhoods has dramatically decreased to 300 m.
155 According to the company ruling the installation, the plant has an annual production
156 close to 1 million of cement tons. Non-conventional fuels (sewage sludge, animal
157 flours, refuse derived fuels, biomass) account 20% of the total energy consumed. The
158 second plant (B) is set in the coastline of southern Catalonia, integrated in a rural
159 background. Apart from the cement manufacture process, limestone mining activities
160 are performed in the nearby of the plant. Close to the cement plant there is a road with
161 an average daily traffic of 12,380 vehicles per day, being 34.4 % of them considered as
162 heavy vehicles (Ministerio de Fomento, 2012). It has been operating since 1968. The
163 closest population nucleus is 3 km away from the plant. In the year 2012 the plant
164 reached a production of 867,353 metric tons of cement. During the same year 31.9% of
165 the total energy consumption came from alternative fuels, which means more than 85.5
166 thousands metric tons yearly. Half of this number is composed by biomass, while the
167 other half is made from refuse derived fuels. Both plants are 165 km away from each
168 other, and they present similar air cleaning devices.

169
170 After running a dispersion model (AERMOD v.12345) (US EPA, 2012) for every
171 cement plant, we assessed the area affected by the cement plume. Within this area, we
172 chose a single sampling point for every location. These points were located into
173 populated nuclei including especially sensitive groups of population (children, seniors,
174 etc.). In location A the sampling point was located 300 m away from the cement plant,
175 while in location B it was located 500 m away from the facility. To evaluate differences
176 among seasons with different meteorological conditions, samples in location A were
177 collected in three periods: autumn 2013 (AA), winter 2013/2014 (AW), and summer
178 2014 (AS). In location B samples were obtained during autumn 2014 (BA). For every
179 period, samples were collected during five consecutive days. Samples were collected
180 simultaneously with three high-volume active samplers, one for each analyzed fraction.
181 PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} were sampled using two TE-6070-DV devices (Tisch Environmental),
182 while PM₁ samples were collected using CAV-A/mb sampler (MCV SA). Volume
183 sampled was around 1700 m³ for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} and around 600 m³ for PM₁. All the
184 three fractions were collected in quartz microfiber filters (QFF).

185 186 *2.2. Analytical methods*

187
188 Before sampling, filters were heated at 200°C for 4 h. PM levels were calculated by
189 gravimetric determination. Filters were acclimated and weighted at constant humidity
190 (40%) and temperature (20°C) during consecutive days until constant weight before and
191 after sampling campaign. Subsequently, filters were divided into three portions to
192 perform different analytical determinations.

193
194 The first portion of filter was used for metals analysis. It was treated with a mixture of 2
195 mL of HNO₃ (65% Suprapur, E.Merck) and 3 mL of HF (37.5%, Panreac) in hermetic
196 Teflon bombs for 8 h at room temperature, and 8 additional hours at 80°C. After
197 cooling, extracts were filtered and made up to 25 mL with ultrapure water. They were
198 kept frozen at -20 °C until further analysis (Mari et al., 2009). Contents of trace
199 elements were determined by means of Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry

200 (ICP-MS, Perkin Elmer Elan 6000), while major elements were determined by means of
201 Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry techniques (ICP-OES,
202 Perkin Elmer, Optima 3200RL). A complete list with all the analyzed elements, as well
203 as their corresponding limits of detection is included in supplementary materials.

204 Another portion of filter was used for the determination of soluble inorganic ions (Cl⁻,
205 SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, and NH₄⁺). The piece of filter was cut in smaller portions and mixed with
206 15 mL of deionised water in a falcon tube. Then, it was shaken during 4 hours and
207 submerged in a sonication bath at 60°C during 1 hour. The extract was then filtered with
208 a 250 µm sieve, and the filtered liquid analyzed by means of Ionic Chromatography and
209 specific electrode (DX-300 Dionex) to elucidate the ionic content. For obtaining the
210 total carbon (TC) content, the last portion of filter was submitted to pyrolysis with
211 oxygen at 1,000 °C. Resulting gases (CO₂ and NO_x) were driven by a helium flow,
212 which was subsequently analyzed by means of gas chromatography (Thermo EA 1108
213 CHNS-O Carlo Erba Instruments) (Tiessen and Moir, 2000a, 2000b). To address the
214 joint content of organic carbon (OC) and elemental carbon (EC), sample was previously
215 exposed to a HCl enriched atmosphere in order to remove the carbon from carbonates.
216 After that it was analyzed following the same methodology described for TC.

217

218 Laboratory reagents blanks and duplicates were performed in order to control the
219 quality of the process. As external standard, Loamy clay soil (National Institute of
220 Standards and Technology) was used for metal and sulphanimide for carbonic content.

221

222 Some indirect calculations were performed in order to find out the contents of different
223 compounds. To establish the OC content we solved the equation $OC = 0.7 \times (OC + EC)$
224 (Pérez et al., 2008). Organic matter (OM) was estimated by applying a factor of 1.6 to
225 organic carbon concentrations (Pérez et al., 2008). Carbonate and SiO₂ content were
226 estimated from Ca and Mg ($1.5 \times Ca + 2.5 \times Mg = CO_3^{2-}$) and Al₂O₃ concentrations (2
227 $\times Al_2O_3 = SiO_2$), respectively (Querol et al., 2001). We assume that the totality of Al
228 analysed was in oxide form (Al₂O₃) (Querol et al., 2001).

229

230 *2.3. Main components determination*

231

232 PM were divided in six main components: mineral matter (Sum of CO₃²⁻, SiO₂, Al₂O₃,
233 Ti, P, Mn, Mg, K, Fe, and Ca), sea spray (sum of Na⁺ and Cl⁻), organic matter and
234 elemental carbon (OM+EC), secondary inorganic aerosols (sum of SO₄²⁻, NH₄⁺, and
235 NO₃⁻), trace elements (the sum of the rest of elements), and unaccounted (the difference
236 between the PM concentration and the sum of the rest of fractions).

237

238 *2.4. Exposure Model*

239

240 Concentrations of harmful metals (As, Be, Cd, Co, Cr, Hg, Mn, Ni, Pb, Se, V, and U) in
241 the different PM fractions, seasons, and locations were used for assessing the human
242 exposure. This metal selection was done according toxicological parameters availability
243 in the risk assessment information system (RAIS, 2013). Exposure of the local
244 population was estimated by considering only the inhalation route for an average adult
245 individual (from 16 to 65 years old) in a mean daily routine based on annual data
246 (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2012). Average exposure was calculated as divided in three
247 different activities: sleeping, working/leisure, and outdoor time. Sleeping and
248 working/leisure were considered as fully indoor activities. Numerical expression and

249 parameters used to evaluate the exposure (Exp) for the different activities are shown in
250 Equation 1:

251

$$252 \quad Exp = \frac{C_{air} \times IR \times EF}{BW \times 365} \times \frac{AcT}{24} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

253

254 Descriptions and values of the different parameters are presented in Table 1. C_{air} used
255 differed between indoor (sleeping and working/leisure) and outdoor activities. C_{air} for
256 outdoor activities was the obtained from analytical determinations. C_{air} for indoor
257 activities was calculated from outdoor C_{air} through the software IAQX v 1.1, developed
258 by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA, 2000). We set an
259 average room volume of 30 m³. Ventilation rates were taken according to the RD
260 1027/2007 specification for domestic and office buildings (IDA 2), published by the
261 Spanish Ministry of Tourism, Energy, and Industry (MINETUR, 2013). Deposition and
262 infiltration rates used in our simulations were obtained from previous studies (He et al.,
263 2005; Hoek et al., 2008). Total exposure was calculated as the sum of every activity
264 exposure (sleeping, work/leisure, and outdoor).

265

266 *2.5. Human Health risks assessment*

267

268 Non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic risks calculations through inhalation were
269 previously described (Rovira et al., 2010). Briefly, exposure concentrations (EC),
270 Hazard Quotient (HQ) and cancer risk are described in equations 2, 3, and 4,
271 respectively.

$$272 \quad EC = \frac{C_{air} \times AcT \times EF \times ED}{AT \times 365 \times 24} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

$$273 \quad HQ = \frac{EC \times 10^6}{RfC} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

$$274 \quad \text{CancerRisk} = EC \times 10^6 \times IUR \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

275

276 All parameters used in these equations are depicted in Table 1.

277

278 In order to know the carcinogenic potential of Cr, we assumed Cr (VI) concentration as
279 1/6 of the total Cr concentration (Brown et al., 2014; US EPA, 2011). It was also
280 assumed that the totality of the As measured was inorganic (Huang et al., 2014).

281

282 *2.6. Statistical Treatment*

283 For the statistical treatment we assumed a concentration equal to half the limit of
284 detection for that species under the detection limit. Statistical processing was carried out
285 by means of the statistical software package SPSS Statistics 20.0. For elucidating if the
286 data present a parametric distribution a Levene test was performed. Subsequently,
287 student T tests and ANOVA (parametric data), and Kruskal Wallis (non-parametric
288 data) tests were undergone. We considered difference as significant for those cases with
289 a probability below 0.05 (p<0.05).

290

291 **3. Results and discussion**

292

293 *3.1. PM concentrations*

294

295 Mean daily PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁ concentrations for the two plants (A and B) and for
296 the different sampling periods: autumn (A), winter (W) and summer (S), are shown in
297 Fig. 1. Statistically significant differences (p<0.05) were found between winter and the
298 other seasons in plant A. The highest concentrations for the three fractions were
299 reported during winter, with average values of 51.2 ± 13.9, 31.9 ± 9.9, and 31.3 ± 7.1
300 µg/m³ for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁, respectively. Comparing the samples collected in
301 summer and autumn, significantly (p<0.05) higher concentrations of PM₁₀ were
302 recorded during autumn. No statistically significant differences were found between
303 PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations obtained in plant B and those obtained in plant A in
304 samples collected during autumn. However, regarding PM₁, statistically significant
305 (p<0.05) smaller concentrations were found in plant B.

306

307 Mean values of the three particle fractions and the seasonal pattern obtained in plant A
308 are similar to those reported previously in the metropolitan area of Barcelona (Pérez et
309 al., 2008). In his turn, levels found in plant B are similar to those described in rural
310 areas previously (Vicente et al. 2011; Pey et al. 2010c; Rodríguez et al. 2004). In our
311 research, yearly limits established by the EU for PM_{2.5} (25 µg/m³), and yearly and daily
312 values set for PM₁₀ (40 and 50 µg/m³, respectively) (EU Parliament, 2008) were surpass
313 only in the plant A in winter.

314

315 3.2. *Main components of PM*

316

317 Fig. 2 shows the main components of the collected particles. The main components
318 considered were organic matter and elemental carbon (OM+EC), sea spray (SS),
319 mineral matter (MM), secondary inorganic aerosols (SIA), trace elements (TE), and
320 unaccounted (U).

321

322 3.2.1. *Organic matter (OM) and elemental carbon (EC)*

323

324 OM+EC is mainly attributable to combustion sources (Pérez et al., 2008). Our results
325 show that this component increases its contribution to the PM in the fine fraction of
326 particles. This trend was described in previous studies (Pérez et al., 2008; Reche et al.,
327 2012). Maximum levels of OM+EC were registered during winter, and reached their
328 minimum in summer for every fraction. An increase in the use of heating systems and
329 road traffic associated to low temperatures seems to be the cause for such result
330 (Galindo et al., 2010).

331

332 In our study, mean levels of OM+EC obtained during winter for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} (19.8
333 and 16.8 µg/m³, respectively) were higher than those recorded previously within the
334 Barcelona metropolitan area (around 11.9 µg/m³ for both fractions) (Viana et al., 2006).
335 These differences could have their origin in different meteorological conditions during
336 sampling collection, differences in heating systems between both places and/or
337 combustion from cement facility. Comparing both cement plants, B location presented
338 smaller values of OM+EC, explained by the lower traffic density.

339

340 3.2.2. *Sea spray (SS)*

341

342 Sea spray was mainly taking part into the PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} fractions, experiencing a
343 great decrease in PM₁. These results are in agreement with previous studies carried out

344 by other authors (Kelly and Fussell, 2012; Mazzei et al., 2008). Higher contributions
345 from this component are recorded in B location due to its proximity to the coastline.

346

347 3.2.3. Mineral matter (MM)

348

349 Maximum contributions of mineral matter are shown in PM₁₀ in winter. During this
350 period, mineral matter contribution decreases notably when the particle size decreases to
351 PM_{2.5}. In autumn, mineral matter shows similar contributions in PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5},
352 decreasing in PM₁. In summer, this component remains constant, between 10-20% for
353 every fraction. Comparing both sites in autumn, cement plant B showed smaller
354 contribution of this parameter in PM₁₀, but similar values to those experienced in plant
355 for the rest of fractions.

356

357 3.2.4. Secondary Inorganic Aerosols (SIA)

358

359 Ammonium and sulphate have been recorded to be present mainly in the fine fraction,
360 while nitrate is usually part of the coarser fraction. For every season and location, SIA
361 contributions show a homogeneous distribution among the three fractions, with values
362 ranging between 12-22%. Comparing plant A and B in the same season, higher
363 ammonium contributions are shown in location B, suggesting a bigger influence from
364 farming activities (Pey et al., 2010b).

365

366 3.2.5. Trace elements (TE)

367

368 Concentrations of all analysed elements for the three fractions can be seen in
369 supplementary materials (Table S1). Levels of toxic metals regulated under the
370 European legislation (As, Cd, Ni, and Pb) were much lower in our study (Table 2) than
371 the annual average limits set by 2008/50/EC and 2004/107/EC Directives (EU
372 Parliament, 2008, 2004). These regulations set mean annual air limits at 6, 5, 20, and
373 500 ng/m³ for As, Cd, Ni, and Pb, respectively.

374

375 Statistically significant differences (p<0.05) were found during the winter period when
376 comparing the levels of different trace elements with the rest of sampling periods.
377 Higher concentrations for almost every metal were observed during the winter within
378 the three analyzed fractions. Especially high are the levels of V within the PM₁₀ fraction
379 in winter. This could be a result of changes in the composition of fuel used in the
380 cement facility (Reche et al., 2012). Levels of Cu, Mn, and Sb in the coarser fraction
381 (Pant and Harrison, 2013), which are used as traffic tracers, show similar values ~~levels~~
382 in winter and autumn, experiencing a great decrease in summer. Comparing both plants
383 in the same season, statistically significant higher (p<0.05) concentrations were
384 recorded in A location for almost the totality of metals analyzed in every fraction. The
385 only metals which registered higher significant levels in plant B were Sc, Mo, and V.
386 These differences were especially clear in the PM_{2.5} and PM₁ fractions, and could be a
387 consequence of the differences in fuel composition between the two plants (Arbuzov et
388 al., 2014; Lane et al., 2013; Santacatalina et al., 2010). Levels of Cu, Mn, and Sb were
389 lower in the coarser fraction of B location, indicating a smaller contribution from traffic
390 sources. Comparing our study with previous studies performed in the area (Pey et al.,
391 2010c; Pérez et al., 2008; Minguillón et al., 2014), similar metal concentrations and
392 seasonal patterns are observed. Plant A shows levels of metals similar to an urban-

393 industrial site, while B presents a slightly higher metal concentrations than those
394 reported for a rural background (Querol et al., 2007).

395

396 3.2.6. *Unaccounted (U)*

397

398 This component expresses the difference between the PM levels and the sum of the rest
399 of main components. Unaccounted contributions range between 2-46% for PM_{2.5} and
400 PM₁. This range decreases in the PM₁₀ fraction, having values between 2-35%. The
401 origin of the unaccounted component is diverse. Previous studies have related this
402 component with water bound to secondary inorganic aerosols, measurement errors or
403 underestimations in the content of OM+EC (Pey et al., 2010a; Santacatalina et al.,
404 2010).

405

406 Except for the concentrations of OM+EC during winter, levels and seasonal patterns of
407 the components in location A for every fraction present in this study are similar to those
408 reported previously in the Barcelona metropolitan area (Pérez et al., 2008; Pey et al.,
409 2010b, 2010c). Location A seems to be more influenced by traffic emissions than
410 location B. Higher contributions in OM+EC could have their origin in traffic exhaust
411 emissions, and contributions to coarse TE could have their source in traffic non-exhaust
412 emissions.

413

414 3.3. *Exposure Model*

415

416 Indoor PM levels and exposure values are shown in Table 3. In order to better assess the
417 exposure to different size of particles, we calculated the health risks for three diameter
418 ranges: PM_{10-2.5} (result of subtracting PM_{2.5} levels to PM₁₀ levels), PM_{2.5-1} (result of
419 subtracting PM₁ levels to PM_{2.5} levels) and PM₁.

420

421 Indoor concentrations represent around 65% of the outdoor concentrations for PM_{2.5-1}
422 and PM₁, and around 45% of the outdoor PM₁₀ concentrations. In location A, the
423 highest values of indoor concentrations are reached in the PM₁ fraction, while location
424 B reaches its greatest values of indoor concentration in the PM_{10-2.5} fraction. This result
425 is a direct consequence of the higher proportion of PM₁ in PM₁₀ found in location A,
426 and a bigger infiltration rate for fine PM. Regarding the activities, working and leisure
427 showed the highest exposures for every period and PM fraction. Consequently, indoor
428 exposure was the highest for every PM fraction due the most of time expended in indoor
429 environment.

430

431 The results of specific metal exposure are shown in Fig. 3. Maximum exposure was
432 reached by V in winter, with a value of $5.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ mg/(kg·day). More than half of this
433 value (54%) was reached in the PM_{10-2.5}. Se and Hg were not detected in any sampling
434 period. Winter was the period that showed highest metal exposure for most of the
435 metals analyzed. During this period, Pb and V levels of exposure were considerably
436 higher (1.6 and 3.1 times respectively) than highest values for the rest of periods.
437 Comparing the two sites in the same season, smaller levels of exposure were detected in
438 location B. In this location, most of the exposure was addressed in the fine fraction,
439 while in location A it was located in the PM_{10-2.5} fraction. The higher metal content
440 from traffic non-exhaust emissions in location A could explain this result.

441

442 Regarding the distribution of different metals, Co, Cd, and Be showed their maximum
443 exposure values in the PM_{10-2.5} fraction. Uranium showed their maximum exposures in
444 PM_{2.5-1}. Peak exposure values of As, Mn, and Pb were experienced in the PM₁ fraction.
445 Apart from traffic, cement facilities could be also a supplementary source of Cd, Co, Cr,
446 Mn, and Ni, and the main contributor for As, Pb, and V (Gupta et al., 2012;
447 Santacatalina et al., 2010). Levels of exposure in plant A were similar to those reported
448 before for the same area (Rovira et al., 2011b).

449

450 *3.4. Human health risks assessment*

451

452 Regarding non-carcinogenic risks, HQ for all the chemicals was below the safety
453 threshold, established in 1. Winter in plant A was the sampling period experiencing the
454 highest levels of non-carcinogenic risks. Within this period, the highest HQ value
455 corresponded to Mn allocated in PM₁, with a HQ value of 0.1. The rest of the HQ
456 values were below 10% of the safety limit.

457

458 Additional carcinogenic risks due to metal inhalation are depicted in Table 4.
459 Hexavalent Cr was the only metal above the threshold for cancer risk established as 10⁻⁵
460 in Spain (MAGRAMA, 2007). This threshold was surpassed in every sampling period,
461 except for plant A during summer. However, cancer values were assumable (10⁻⁶–10⁻⁴)
462 depending on the variable characteristics of each individual (US EPA, 1996). The
463 sampling period performed in winter experienced the highest levels of carcinogenic risk
464 for most of metals. This period reached the highest overall value of additional cancer
465 risk, with a value of 2.9 10⁻⁵ for Cr (VI). In winter, most of the additional carcinogenic
466 risks observed were part of the PM_{2.5-1} or PM₁ fractions. Unlike winter, most of the
467 additional carcinogenic risks observed in autumn and summer were located in the PM₁₀₋
468 _{2.5} fraction. As observed with OM+EC, a higher contribution from combustion sources
469 (such as heating systems) in winter could be the explanation to this fact.

470

471 Carcinogenic risks were smaller in plant B if compared with plant A in the same season
472 of the year. In this location, most of additional carcinogenic risks were in the PM₁
473 fraction. The presence of toxic metals in the fine fraction in location B suggests a higher
474 contribution to metal content from combustion processes, such as the cement production
475 (Kelly and Fussell, 2012).

476

477 PM₁ registers the maximum carcinogenic risk in the case of As and Pb, and the highest
478 overall value for Cr (IV), evidencing thus the damage potential of PM₁. As said
479 previously, As and Pb are elements suitable for coming principally from the cement
480 plant. Although Cr (VI) is not an exclusive metal from cement production, it is feasible
481 a contribution to this metal levels from the cement facility, especially in plant B, where
482 traffic is less intense and no other industrial activities are developed. Levels of risks for
483 most of the metals here described are similar to those previously reported in the same
484 area (Rovira et al., 2011b).

485

486 **4. Conclusions**

487

488 In this study, three fractions of PM (10, 2.5, and 1) were collected in the nearby area of
489 two cement plants in different seasons. Main components, exposure, and human health
490 risks were calculated to preliminary know the main contributors to the PM mass and
491 evaluate the potential health effects on the population. Our results show greatest levels

492 of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁ during winter. During this season, the highest levels of
493 OM+EC and toxic metals were registered for every PM fraction. Consequently,
494 exposure and human health risks experienced their highest values. Summer and autumn
495 show similar levels of PM mass, but with a greater contribution from combustion
496 sources in autumn. Comparing both plants in the same season, statistically significant
497 differences were found in the levels of PM₁ and TE, presenting lower values plant B.
498 Differences in the concentrations of Sc, Mo, and V between the two locations suggest
499 the influence of the cement plant fuel used in the ambient particles composition,
500 especially in the PM₁ fraction. Traffic had a major contribution to ambient PM in
501 location A, while in location B, less impacted by traffic, cement plant had more
502 influence, especially in the fine fraction.

503

504 Exposure values were higher for indoor activities (working/leisure and sleeping) due the
505 most of time expended in indoor environment. Non-carcinogenic risks were below the
506 safety threshold (HQ<1). Carcinogenic risks for most of the metals were below the limit
507 of 10⁻⁵, except for Cr (VI), which exceeded it in both locations, but being in the range
508 considered as assumable (10⁻⁶-10⁻⁴).

509

510 In this preliminary study, the importance of working on fine PM in areas influenced by
511 cement plants is revealed. Maximum values of carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risks
512 were observed in the ambient PM₁. A possible contribution from cement plants to
513 OM+EC and elements (especially As and Pb) in the ambient PM₁ is observed in this
514 work. Further research, with greater number of samples and more detailed exposure
515 evaluation for different ages and activities of indoor concentrations, is needed in order
516 to elucidate the real contribution from different sources to human health damages.

517

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519

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525

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Table 1: Parameters used for calculating human exposure and health risks

Parameter	Description	Value	Units	Reference	
IR	Inhalation rate	Sleeping	7.58	m ³ /day	OEHHA 2012
		Work/Leisure	38.8		
		Outdoor	38.8		
EF	Exposure frequency	350	days/year	MAGRAMA, 2007	
BW	Body weight	70	kg	US EPA, 1989	
AcT	Activity Time	Sleeping	8.88	hours/day	Generalitat de Catalunya, 2012
		Work/Leisure	12.7		
		Outdoor	2.40		
ED	Exposure duration	30	years	MAGRAMA, 2007	
AT	Averaging time	Carcinogenic: 70	years	MAGRAMA, 2007	
		Non-carcinogenic: 30			
RfC	Reference inhalation concentration	As	1.50E+01	ng/m ³	RAIS, 2013
		Be	2.00E+01		
		Cd	2.00E+01		
		Co	6.00E+00		
		Cr	1.00E+02		
		Hg	3.00E+02		
		Mn	5.00E+01		
		Ni	9.00E+01		
		Se	2.00E+04		
		V	1.00E+02		
IUR	Inhalation Unit Risk	As	4.3E-06	m ³ /ng	RAIS, 2013
		Be	2.4E-06		
		Cd	1.8E-06		
		Co	9.0E-06		
		Cr	8.4E-05		
		Ni	2.6E-07		
		Pb	1.2E-08		
	Conversion factor	365	days/year		
	Conversion factor	24	hour/day		
	Conversion factor	10 ⁶	ng/mg		
C _{air}	Concentration in air	Site Specific	mg/m ³	Present study	

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Table 2: Levels (mean ± standard deviation) of toxic elements for both cement plants (A and B), and sampling periods: autumn (A), winter (W), and summer (S). Results are expressed in ng/m³.

	AA			AW			AS			BA		
	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁
As	0.63 ± 0.09	0.38 ± 0.07	0.36 ± 0.11	0.62 ± 0.13	0.59 ± 0.06	0.39 ± 0.21	0.19 ± 0.07	ND	ND	0.36 ± 0.16	0.30 ± 0.02	0.15 ± 0.10
Be	0.09 ± 0.03	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Cd	0.68 ± 0.35	0.31 ± 0.13	0.26 ± 0.05	0.47 ± 0.01	0.20 ± 0.01	0.20 ± 0.01	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Co	0.33 ± 0.06	0.09 ± 0.03	0.08 ± 0.06	0.45 ± 0.27	0.15 ± 0.09	0.10 ± 0.02	0.15 ± 0.02	ND	ND	0.20 ± 0.10	0.11 ± 0.02	0.08 ± 0.01
Cr	7.28 ± 0.22	ND	ND	8.49 ± 3.09	4.20 ± 1.32	4.18 ± 3.26	3.26 ± 0.53	ND	ND	6.05 ± 0.70	6.02 ± 2.84	ND
Mn	6.98 ± 3.94	4.38 ± 1.02	3.32 ± 3.67	8.13 ± 2.82	7.48 ± 1.38	5.29 ± 2.47	7.85 ± 2.30	1.91 ± 0.91	1.89 ± 0.46	5.10 ± 3.32	2.83 ± 1.23	1.33 ± 0.70
Ni	4.07 ± 0.91	1.74 ± 0.14	1.6 ± 0.18	6.96 ± 2.42	5.94 ± 4.33	1.69 ± 0.94	7.0E ± 2.42	ND	ND	3.47 ± 0.47	3.24 ± 0.66	2.88 ± 0.69
Pb	11.9 ± 3.19	4.96 ± 1.76	4.07 ± 2.64	16.8 ± 3.03	13.2 ± 4.89	13.1 ± 3.88	3.16 ± 1.62	1.70 ± 2.21	1.29 ± 0.86	3.57 ± 2.57	2.88 ± 1.93	1.61 ± 0.96
U	0.11 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.06	0.15 ± 0.04	0.15 ± 0.03	0.15 ± 0.07	0.02 ± 0.02	ND	ND	0.08 ± 0.06	0.08 ± 0.06	ND
V	6.87 ± 3.03	3.15 ± 0.57	2.22 ± 0.85	23.5 ± 8.95	9.09 ± 2.57	4.44 ± 1.02	6.57 ± 3.79	3.04 ± 0.05	2.85 ± 0.15	7.28 ± 1.02	6.36 ± 2.52	6.07 ± 1.85

ND: Not detected.

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714 **Table 3: Indoor and outdoor PM concentrations and exposure levels for both cement plants (A and**
 715 **B), and sampling periods: autumn (A), winter (W), and summer (S).**
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		PM concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)		Exposure ($\text{mg}/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{day})$)		
		Outdoor	Indoor	Sleeping	Working/Leisure	Outdoor
AA	PM _{10-2.5}	9.68	4.36	1.7E-04	1.2E-03	5.1E-04
	PM _{2.5-1}	0.16	0.10	4.0E-06	2.9E-05	8.5E-06
	PM ₁	16.8	10.9	4.2E-04	3.1E-03	9.0E-04
	Total	26.7	15.4	5.9E-04	4.3E-03	1.4E-03
AW	PM _{10-2.5}	19.3	8.68	3.3E-04	2.4E-03	1.0E-03
	PM _{2.5-1}	0.67	0.44	1.7E-05	1.2E-04	3.6E-05
	PM ₁	31.3	20.3	7.8E-04	5.7E-03	1.7E-03
	Total	51.2	29.4	1.1E-03	8.3E-03	2.7E-03
AS	PM _{10-2.5}	1.04	0.47	1.8E-05	1.3E-04	5.5E-05
	PM _{2.5-1}	6.51	4.23	1.6E-04	1.2E-03	3.5E-04
	PM ₁	13.0	8.42	3.2E-04	2.4E-03	6.9E-04
	Total	20.5	13.1	5.0E-04	3.7E-03	1.1E-03
BA	PM _{10-2.5}	15.0	6.76	2.6E-04	1.9E-03	8.0E-04
	PM _{2.5-1}	8.82	5.73	2.2E-04	1.6E-03	4.7E-04
	PM ₁	6.12	3.98	1.5E-04	1.1E-03	3.3E-04
	Total	30.0	16.5	6.3E-04	4.6E-03	1.6E-03

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Table 4: Carcinogenic risk due to the exposure to metals associated to different PM fractions for both cement plants (A and B), and sampling periods: autumn (A), winter (W), and summer (S).

		As	Be	Cd	Co	Cr (VI)	Ni	Pb
AA	PM _{10-2.5}	2.2E-07	4.3E-08	1.4E-07	4.5E-07	2.1E-05	1.3E-07	1.7E-08
	PM _{2.5-1}	2.4E-08	NC	2.8E-08	3.4E-08	NC	1.0E-08	3.0E-09
	PM ₁	4.3E-07	NC	NC	1.3E-07	NC	1.2E-07	1.4E-08
	Total	6.8E-07	4.3E-08	1.7E-07	6.1E-07	2.1E-05	2.5E-07	3.4E-08
AW	PM _{10-2.5}	2.5E-08	NC	1.0E-07	5.6E-07	1.2E-05	5.5E-08	8.8E-09
	PM _{2.5-1}	2.4E-07	NC	1.4E-09	1.1E-07	6.5E-08	3.1E-07	4.7E-10
	PM ₁	4.7E-07	NC	1.0E-07	2.6E-07	1.6E-05	1.2E-07	4.4E-08
	Total	7.4E-07	NC	2.0E-07	9.4E-07	2.9E-05	4.9E-07	5.4E-08
AS	PM _{10-2.5}	1.7E-07	NC	NC	2.8E-07	9.5E-06	3.8E-07	3.6E-09
	PM _{2.5-1}	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC	1.4E-09
	PM ₁	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC	4.4E-09
	Total	1.7E-07	NC	NC	2.8E-07	9.5E-06	3.8E-07	9.4E-09
BA	PM _{10-2.5}	5.4E-08	NC	NC	1.6E-07	7.9E-08	1.2E-08	1.7E-09
	PM _{2.5-1}	1.8E-07	NC	NC	9.6E-08	2.0E-05	2.5E-08	4.3E-09
	PM ₁	1.8E-07	NC	NC	1.9E-07	NC	2.1E-07	5.4E-09
	Total	4.2E-07	NC	NC	4.5E-07	2.0E-05	2.5E-07	1.1E-08

NC: Not calculated. Values under the limit of detection

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Fig. 1: Daily mean PM_{10} (a), $PM_{2.5}$ (b), and PM_1 (c) levels for both cement plants (A and B), and sampling periods: autumn (A), winter (W), and summer (S). Different superscripted letters denote statistical significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 2: Main components of collected PM for both cement plants (A and B), and sampling periods: autumn (A), winter (W), and summer (S). Results are expressed as percentage of the mass.

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Fig. 3: Metal exposure levels for both cement plants (A and B), and sampling periods: autumn (A), winter (W), and summer (S).

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